

2022

Supplementary material 1: Risk analysis report for *Cenchrus setaceus* in Kruger National Park – a case study

**For: A FRAMEWORK FOR CONDUCTING RISK ANALYSES
FOR ALIEN SPECIES
IN SOUTH AFRICAN NATIONAL PARKS**

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Risk analysis summary

<p>Species: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (fountain grass)</p>	<p>Area: Kruger National Park (KNP)</p>
<p>Compiled by: Nkuna, Khensani Vulani</p>	<p>Date of assessment: Date submitted & where:</p>
<p>Picture of Species</p> <p>https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?country=US&has_coordinate=true&has_geospatial_issue=false&taxon_key=5828232</p>	
<p>Risk Assessment summary: Fountain grass (<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>) was introduced into the Kruger National Park (KNP) as a garden ornamental plant. The savanna biome of the park is a suitable habitat and climatic suitability are met at a large scale. <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a fire promoting grass with the potential to transform ecosystems if it becomes invasive. It has been reported to reduce native species richness through direct competition for resources such as soil nutrients, space, and light. It is prolific outside the park along roadsides and other disturbed areas. Spread of <i>C. setaceus</i> is primarily aided by humans intentionally as an ornamental or unintentional as transport stowaway.</p>	<p>Risk score: High</p>
<p>Management options summary: Any possible socio-economic (ornamental) and environmental (soil stabiliser) benefits of <i>C. setaceus</i> in the park are not considered as they do not contribute to the park's objectives. Populations of <i>C. setaceus</i> in KNP are moderately accessible as they are currently found only in residential areas of the park. However, the propagules (seeds and whole plant) are long-lived and highly persistent, and plants start to reproduce in less than one year which can make management difficult. An eradication or extirpation feasibility evaluation has not been conducted for the park or other protected areas, but because <i>C. setaceus</i> is widespread outside the park, with large populations in the Phalaborwa region, it is therefore unlikely that eradication is feasible.</p>	<p>Ease of management: Difficult</p>
<p>Recommended goal: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a low priority <i>Species</i> as per the RAAS framework. However, because there are no known invasive populations occurring outside cultivation in the park, it is recommended to control individuals and small populations that might be found in natural areas. Management efforts should be focus on surveillance, especially along the boundaries and buffer zone of the Phalaborwa area. It is also recommended that KNP alien species management engages with relevant authorities outside the park to collaborate in the management of <i>C. setaceus</i> and to encourage measures to prevent entry of the <i>Species</i> into the park.</p>	<p>Listing under NEMBA A&IS regulations 2020: - 1b category - listed as <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> - Sterile cultivars or hybrids are not listed.</p> <p>KNP Priority level: Low priority</p>

1. Background

BAC1 Name of assessor(s)	
Name of lead assessor	Khensani V. Nkuna
BAC2 Contact details of assessor (s)	
Lead assessor	Organisational affiliation: South African National Parks (SANParks-Kruger National Park) Email: khensani.vulani@sanparks.org Phone: 0825946710
BAC3 Name(s) and contact details of expert(s) consulted	
Expert (1)	Name: Llewellyn C. Foxcroft Email: llewellyn.foxcroft@sanparks.org Phone: (013) 735 4124 Expertise: Invasion ecology scientist in KNP
Expert (2)	Name: Nikisha Singh Email: Nikisha.Singh@sanparks.org Phone: (013) 735 4140 Expert: Biological reference collection curator KNP
Comments: Experts were selected based on their experience and knowledge of the <i>Species</i> under assessment, and were consulted on an ad hoc basis.	
BAC4 Scientific name of <i>Species</i> under assessment	
<i>Species</i> name: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>	Authority: (Forssk.) Morrone
Comments: The <i>Species</i> <i>C. setaceus</i> was previously named <i>Phalaris setacea</i> and later <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (Chemisquy et al. 2010, Veldkamp 2014).	
References: Chemisquy MA, Giussani LM, Scatagliani MA, Kellogg EA, Morrone O. (2010) Phylogenetic studies favour the unification of <i>Pennisetum</i> , <i>Cenchrus</i> and <i>Odontelytrum</i> (Poaceae): a combined nuclear, plastid and morphological analysis, and nomenclatural combinations in <i>Cenchrus</i> . <i>Annals of botany</i> , 106 (1): 107–30. Veldkamp JF. (2014) A revision of <i>Cenchrus</i> incl. <i>Pennisetum</i> (Gramineae) in Malasia with some general nomenclatural notes. <i>Blumea-Biodiversity, Evolution and Biogeography of Plants</i> , 59 (1): 59–75.	
BAC5 Synonym(s) considered	
Synonyms: <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> ; <i>Phalaris setacea</i>	
Comments: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> was previously named <i>Phalaris setacea</i> Forssk and later changed to <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (CABI 2021, Catalogue of Life 2021, ITIS 2021). However, recent molecular research has confirmed that the genus <i>Cenchrus</i> and <i>Pennisetum</i> should be united, thus the <i>Species</i> has been changed again from <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> to <i>C. setaceus</i> (Chemisquy et al. 2010, Donadio, et al. 2009, Veldkamp 2014). Although <i>C. setaceus</i> is the current accepted taxonomic name, all three names were used during the literature search in order to include literature conducted before the changes. The <i>Species</i> will only be referred to as <i>C. setaceus</i> in this report.	
References: Catalogue of Life. (2021) Species Details: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Morrone. http://www.catalogueoflife.org/annual-checklist/2018/details/species/id/0f035b63945c983864c76eeb39a13a75/synonym/a39416e827b3e9660661a63b54f573fc . Accessed 20-04-2021.	

<p>Centre for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI). (2021) <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (fountain grass). In: Invasive Species Compendium. Wallingford, UK: CAB International. https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/116202. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p> <p>Chemisquy MA, Giussani LM, Scataglini MA, Kellogg EA, Morrone O. (2010) Phylogenetic studies favour the unification of <i>Pennisetum</i>, <i>Cenchrus</i> and <i>Odontelytrum</i> (Poaceae): a combined nuclear, plastid and morphological analysis, and nomenclatural combinations in <i>Cenchrus</i>. <i>Annals of botany</i>, 106 (1): 107–30.</p> <p>Donadío S, Giussani LM, Kellogg EA, Zuolaga FO, Morrone O. (2009) A preliminary molecular phylogeny of <i>Pennisetum</i> and <i>Cenchrus</i> (Poaceae-Panicaceae) based on the trnL-F, rpl16 chloroplast markers. <i>Taxon</i>, 58 (2): 392–404.</p> <p>Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS). (2021) <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Morrone, Taxonomic Serial No.: 796732. https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=518864#null. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p> <p>Veldkamp JF. (2014) A revision of <i>Cenchrus</i> incl. <i>Pennisetum</i> (Gramineae) in Malasia with some general nomenclatural notes. <i>Blumea-Biodiversity, Evolution and Biogeography of Plants</i>, 59 (1): 59–75.</p>	
BAC6 Common name(s) considered	
Common names: Fountain grass	
Comments: The <i>Species</i> has several common names based on different languages and regions, for example, crimson fountain grass, African fountain grass, tender fountain grass, pronkgras (Afrikaans), afrikanisches lampenputzergras (German), fjäderborstgräs (Sweden), plumacho (Spanish). However, only the common name “fountain grass” is considered in this report as it is the most commonly used in the <i>Area</i> under assessment (Fish et al. 2015, Henderson 2001, ISSA 2021).	
References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. <i>Strelitzia</i> 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Henderson L. (2001) Alien Weeds and Invasive Plants: a Complete Guide to Declared Weeds and Invaders in South Africa. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook, 12. Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> . http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum . Accessed 20-04-2021.	
BAC7 What is the native range of the <i>Species</i>? (see map in Appendix BAC7)	
Response: Northern and Eastern Africa, Middle East and South-west Asia	Confidence: High
Comments: See map in Appendix BAC7.	
References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. <i>Strelitzia</i> 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). (2021) Species profile: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> . http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=309 . Accessed on 23-04-2021. Keyserver. (2021) Weeds of Australia, fact sheet index- <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Morrone. https://keyservers.lucidcentral.org/weeds/data/media/Html/cenchrus_setaceus.htm#Origin . Accessed 20-04-2021.	
BAC8 What is the global alien range of the <i>Species</i>? (see map in Appendix BAC8)	
Response: North America, Europe, Central America and the Caribbean, Oceania, South America, Australia, Southern Africa (Zambia, Zimbabwe, Namibia, Swaziland, and South Africa)	Confidence: High
Comments:	

See map in Appendix BAC8.		
References: Batianoff GN, Butler DW. (2002) Assessment of invasive naturalized plants in south-east Queensland. <i>Plant Protection Quarterly</i> , 17(1): 27–34. Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. <i>Strelitzia</i> 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). (2021) Species profile: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> . http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=309 . Accessed on 23-04-2021. Joubert DF, Cunningham PL. (2002) The distribution and invasive potential of fountain grass <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> in Namibia. <i>Dinteria</i> , 27: 37–47. Keyserver. (2021) Weeds of Australia, fact sheet index- <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Morrone. https://keyserver.lucidcentral.org/weeds/data/media/Html/cenchrus_setaceus.htm#Origin . Accessed 20-04-2021.		
BAC9 Geographic scope = the Area under consideration		
Area of assessment: Kruger National Park (KNP)		
Comments: See map in Appendix 10a.		
BAC10 Is the Species present in the Area? (see map in Appendix BAC10a and images in Appendix BAC10b)		
Response: Yes		Confidence: High
Comments: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> was first recorded in the KNP in 1953, it was introduced into the park for ornamental purposes (Foxcroft et al. 2003, 2008).		
References: Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. <i>Koedoe</i> , 46 (2): 21–44. Foxcroft LC, Richardson DM, Wilson JR (2008) Ornamental Plants as Invasive Aliens: Problems and Solutions in Kruger National Park, South Africa. <i>Environmental Management</i> , 41: 32–51.		
BAC11 Availability of physical specimen		
Response: Yes		Confidence in ID: High
Herbarium or museum accession number: KNP0000791-0 (KNP herbarium) PRE0016766-0 (National Herbarium, Pretoria)		
References: South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI). (2016) Botanical Database of Southern Africa (BODATSA) [<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>]. doi: to be assigned. Accessed 20-04- 2021.		
BAC12 Is the Species native to the Area or part of the Area?		
The <i>Species</i> is native to (part of) the <i>Area</i> .	No	Confidence: High
The <i>Species</i> is alien in (part of) the <i>Area</i> .	Yes	Confidence: High
Comments: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is alien to Southern Africa where the <i>Area</i> under assessment (KNP) is located (Fish et al. 2015, Henderson and Wilson 2017, Rahlao et al. 2010).		
References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. <i>Strelitzia</i> 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Henderson L, Wilson JR. (2017) Changes in the composition and distribution of alien plants in South Africa: An update from the Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas. <i>Bothalia - African Biodiversity & Conservation</i> , 47(2): 1–26.		

Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. <i>Weed research</i> , 50(6): 537–543.		
BAC13 What is the <i>Species'</i> introduction status in the <i>Area</i>?		
The <i>Species</i> is in cultivation/containment.	Yes (Garden ornamental)	Confidence: High
The <i>Species</i> is present outside of cultivation/containment.	Yes (unconfirmed)	Confidence: Medium
The <i>Species</i> has established/naturalised.	Don't know	Confidence: Medium
The <i>Species</i> is invasive.	Don't know	Confidence: Low
<p>Comments:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> occurs in cultivation as an ornamental plant in the staff villages of the KNP (Foxcroft et al. 2003), specifically Skukuza, Houtboschrand and Phalaborwa staff village (Foxcroft et al. 2008). However, the distribution of <i>C. setaceus</i> outside cultivated areas or villages is currently unknown. A survey conducted in 2020 by Keet et al. (submitted) indicate that populations previously recorded to occur at some of the KNP camps (e.g. Houtboschrand) are no longer present, while those in the Phalaborwa and Skukuza staff villages still occur. A large population of <i>C. setaceus</i> occurs on the borders (outside) of the park in the Phalaborwa mines.</p>		
<p>References:</p> <p>Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. <i>Koedoe</i>, 46 (2): 21–44.</p> <p>Foxcroft LC, Richardson DM, Wilson JRU (2008) Ornamental Plants as Invasive Aliens: Problems and Solutions in Kruger National Park, South Africa. <i>Environmental Management</i>, 41: 32–51.</p> <p>Keet J-H, Foxcroft LC, Kumschick S, Nichols GR, Richardson DM, Wilson JRU, Datta A. (submitted) Assessing the effectiveness of alien plant regulations: insights from Kruger National Park, South Africa.</p>		
BAC14 Primary (introduction) pathways		
Release	No	Confidence: Low
Escape	Yes	Confidence: High
Contaminant	No	Confidence: Low
Stowaway	Yes	Confidence: Low
Corridor	Yes	Confidence: Low
Unaided	No	Confidence: Low
<p>Comments:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> has been used in the residential areas of Kruger Nation Park for ornamental purposes, and it is highly likely that this usage is the primary introduction pathway of <i>C. setaceus</i> into the park (Foxcroft et al. 2008). Elsewhere within South Africa, <i>C. setaceus</i> occurs in disturbed areas and along roads (Fish et al. 2015, Rahlao et al. 2010), it is therefore possible that it was also introduced as a transport stowaway of visitors frequenting the park or through interconnected waterways.</p>		
<p>References:</p> <p>Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. <i>Strelitzia</i> 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria.</p> <p>Foxcroft LC, Richardson DM, Wilson JRU (2008) Ornamental Plants as Invasive Aliens: Problems and Solutions in Kruger National Park, South Africa. <i>Environmental Management</i>, 41: 32–51.</p> <p>Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. <i>Weed research</i>, 50(6): 537–543.</p>		

2. Likelihood

LIK1 Likelihood of entry via unaided primary pathways	
Response: Probable (1)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> was recorded as naturalised in the KNP by Foxcroft et al. (2003), it is however unknown whether naturalised populations of <i>C. setaceus</i> occurs outside cultivation. Therefore, the likelihood of unaided entry is probable as per the framework. However, the likelihood of entry via unaided pathways would be “fairly probable” if <i>C. setaceus</i> was not yet present in the Area. This is because although the <i>Species</i> is sessile, it is a prolific invader across South Africa (Chippindall and Crook 1976, Fish et al. 2015, Rahlao et al. 2010), and the possibility of it to enter unaided through interconnected waterways or wind dispersal is highly likely (Milton et al. 2008). A large population of <i>C. setaceus</i> occurs on the borders of the KNP around the Phalaborwa area and birds such as the white-browed sparrow weavers (<i>Plocepasser mahali</i>) use dry <i>C. setaceus</i> and other grasses to construct nests and can possibly introduction the <i>Species</i> into the Park (Keyserver, 2021).</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Chippindall LK, Crook A O. (1976) 240 grasses of Southern Africa. MO Collins.</p> <p>Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria.</p> <p>Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. Koedoe, 46 (2): 21–44.</p> <p>Keyserver. (2021) Weeds of Australia, fact sheet index- <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Morrone. https://keyserver.lucidcentral.org/weeds/data/media/Html/cenchrus_setaceus.htm#Origin. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p> <p>Milton SJ, Dean WRJ, Rahlao SJ. (2008) Evidence for induced pseudo-vivipary in <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (fountain grass) invading a dry river, arid Karoo, South Africa. South African Journal of Botany, 74 (2): 348–349.</p> <p>Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.</p>	
LIK2 Likelihood of entry via human aided primary pathways	
Response: Probable (1)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> already occurs in the KNP, therefore, the likelihood of entry via human aided pathways is probable as per the framework. However, if <i>C. setaceus</i> was not yet present in the park the likelihood of entry via human aided pathways would be unlikely. This is because intentional introductions of plants for any purpose (i.e. ornamental) is regulated within the park (Foxcroft et al. 2003).</p> <p>Although <i>C. setaceus</i> seems not to be invasive on the boarders of the park some accidental human aided introductions, for example as transport contaminant or stowaways, are inevitable (Rahlao et al. 2010).</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. Koedoe, 46 (2): 21–44.</p> <p>Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.</p>	
LIK3 Habitat suitability	
Response: Probable (1)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is mostly invasive in the tropical, sub-tropical and warmer temperate regions of the world (GISD 2021). It has high phenotypic plasticity allowing it to establish in a wide range of</p>	

habitats (CABI 2021). In South Africa, *C. setaceus* is abundant in the disturbed areas, road verges, railways, waste areas, and erosion gullies of the Karoo, Fynbos, and Savanna (Milton et al. 1998, Rahlao et al. 2010, 2014). *Cenchrus setaceus* is also considered a desert plant because it thrives where annual rainfall is less than 100 mm, but it also occurs in higher areas with >600 mm of rain (Milton et al. 1998, Joubert and Cunningham 2002, Tunison 1992). Some regions in KNP experience a long-term average of < 400 mm per year, but with most of the KNP having a long-term average of between 400 mm – 700 mm (MacFadyen et al. 2018). Suitable soil is well-drained/loamy, sandy, or clay but it does not tolerate saline or acidic soils well (Milton et al. 1998; 2008). Thus, key biotic habitat conditions for *C. setaceus* are met in a large terrestrial part of the KNP (Henderson and Wilson 2017).

References:

Centre for Agriculture and Biosciences International (CABI). (2021) *Pennisetum setaceum* (fountain grass). In: Invasive Species Compendium. Wallingford, UK: CAB International. <https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/116202>. Accessed 20-04-2021.

Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). (2021) Species profile: *Cenchrus setaceus*. <http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=309>. Accessed on 23-04-2021.

Henderson L, Wilson JR. (2017) Changes in the composition and distribution of alien plants in South Africa: An update from the Southern African Plant Invaders Atlas. *Bothalia - African Biodiversity & Conservation*, 47(2): 1–26.

Joubert DF, Cunningham PL. (2002) The distribution and invasive potential of fountain grass *Pennisetum setaceum* in Namibia. *Dinteria*, 27: 37–47.

MacFadyen S, Zambatis N, Van Teeffelen AJA, Hui C. (2018) Long-term rainfall regression surfaces for the Kruger National Park, South Africa: a spatio-temporal review of patterns from 1981 to 2015. *International Journal of Climatology*, 38: 2506–2519.

Milton SJ, Dean WRJ, Rahlao SJ. (2008) Evidence for induced pseudo-vivipary in *Pennisetum setaceum* (fountain grass) invading a dry river, arid Karoo, South Africa. *South African Journal of Botany*, 74 (2): 348–349.

Milton SJ, Hoffmann JH, Bowie RCK, D'amico J, Griffiths M, Joubert D, Loewenthal D, Moinde NN, Seymour C, Toral-Granda MV, Wiseman R. (1998) Invasive fountain grass on the Cape Peninsula. *South African Journal of Science* 94 (2): 57–58.

Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive *Pennisetum setaceum* along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. *Weed research*, 50(6): 537–543.

Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2014) Performance of invasive alien fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*) along a climatic gradient through three South African biomes. *South African Journal of Botany*, 91: 43–48.

Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. *Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i: management and research*. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376–393.

LIK4 Climate suitability

Response: Probable (1)

Confidence: High

Rationale:

A study by Rahlao et al. (2014) predicted the climate suitability of *C. setaceus* to include nearly 33% of South Africa's land surface, including a large part of KNP. Outside of the park, *C. setaceus* is prolific across several biomes including the savanna biome (Rahlao et al. 2009, 2014). The population of *C. setaceus* occurring along the KNP borders in the Phalaborwa area also indicates the high climatic suitability of the species in the park. The likelihood of *C. setaceus* to find suitable climatic conditions in the KNP is therefore probable as per the framework.

References:

Rahlao, S.J., 2009. Potential distribution and spread of an invasive alien grass, *Pennisetum setaceum*, in western South Africa. PhD Thesis, Stellenbosch University.

Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2014) Performance of invasive alien fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*) along a climatic gradient through three South African biomes. South African Journal of Botany, 91: 43–48.

LIK5 Unaided secondary (dispersal) pathways

Response: Fairly probably (0.5)

Confidence: High

Rationale:

Inflorescence (100-250 mm long) of *C. setaceus* is light and feathery with hairy spikelets (16-40 mm long) that can be dispersed easily from an invaded to a non-invaded area by wind, floating on water, or carried by birds and possibly ants (Joubert and Cunningham 2008, keyserver 2021, Rahlao et al. 2014, 2010, Tunison 1992, ISSA 2021). *Cenchrus setaceus* is sessile but its dispersal vectors are highly mobile, for example birds and small mammals utilize *C. setaceus* to build nests, thus the likelihood of unaided dispersal is fairly probable.

References:

- Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - *Pennisetum setaceum*. <http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum>. Accessed 20-04-2021.
- Joubert DF, Cunningham PL. (2002) The distribution and invasive potential of fountain grass *Pennisetum setaceum* in Namibia. *Dinteria*, 27: 37–47.
- Keyserver. (2021) Weeds of Australia, fact sheet index- *Cenchrus setaceus* (Forssk.) Morrone. https://keyserver.lucidcentral.org/weeds/data/media/Html/cenchrus_setaceus.htm#Origin. Accessed 20-04-2021.
- Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive *Pennisetum setaceum* along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. *Weed research*, 50(6): 537–543.
- Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2014) Performance of invasive alien fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*) along a climatic gradient through three South African biomes. *South African Journal of Botany*, 91: 43–48.
- Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. *Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i: management and research*. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376–393.

LIK6 Human aided secondary (dispersal) pathways

Response: Unlikely (0.027)

Confidence: High

Rationale:

Cenchrus setaceus is an ornamental garden species and it can be spread intentionally through the horticultural trade (Tunison 1992). However, this pathway is regulated within the KNP, i.e. no plants native or alien are allowed to enter intentionally into the park without a permit. Plants may also not be moved between camps or staff gardens. Most ornamentals previously planted in the staff villages and the camp sites have been removed by the KNP Alien Biota control section. Therefore, there is low probability of spreading *C. setaceus* in the KNP intentionally.

Cenchrus setaceus is present in places (e.g. roadsides) frequented by humans and its seeds can be attached to clothing and transportation as transport stowaways (Donaldson and Rafferty 2002, Rahlao et al. 2010). Be that as it may, the likelihood of human aided dispersal of *C. setaceus* is unlikely due to the regulations that forbid movement of unauthorised species within KNP.

References:

- Donaldson S, Rafferty D. (2002) Identification and Management of fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum* Forsk. Chiov.). University of Nevada-Reno, Cooperative extension. Fact Sheet-02–50
- Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive *Pennisetum setaceum* along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. *Weed research*, 50(6): 537–543.
- Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. *Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i:*

management and research. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376–393.

CALCULATIONS FOR THE LIKELIHOOD SCORE: = Fairly probable (0.5)

Parameter	Likelihood	Stages	Final assessment
LIK1	1	P(entry) = 1	P (invasion) = 0.5
LIK2	1		
LIK3	1	P(establishment) = 1	
LIK4	1		
LIK5	0.5	P (spread) = 0.5	
LIK6	0.027		

3. Impacts

IMP1 Environmental impact	
IMP1a: Competition	
Response: Major (MR)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> has invaded over 100 000 hectares on the leeward (dry) side of the Hawaii island, and it dominates the understorey of the endemic native north Kona dry forests (Cordell and Sandquist 2008). According to Cordell and Sandquist (2008), <i>C. setaceus</i> has direct competition for water in the upper soil profile with native species. <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is also considered a highly competitive invader in Australia, Fiji, French Polynesia and New Caledonia (Joubert and Cunningham 2002). On islands, <i>C. setaceus</i> has been associated with the local extinction of native grass species. For example, in arid habitats of O’ahu and the Hawai’i Islands the native grass <i>Heteropogon contortus</i> has been replaced by <i>C. setaceus</i> (Daehler and Carino 1998, Goergen and Daehler 2002). In Southern Africa, <i>C. setaceus</i> competes and coexists with relatively mesic native grasses such as <i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i>, <i>Heteropogon contortus</i>, and <i>Panicum maximum</i> in different habitats (Joubert and Cunningham 2002).</p>	
References:	
<p>Cordell S, Sandquist DR. (2008) The impact of an invasive African bunchgrass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) on water availability and productivity of canopy trees within a tropical dry forest in Hawaii. <i>Functional Ecology</i>, 22 (6): 1008–1017.</p> <p>Daehler CC, Carino DA. (1998) Recent replacement of native pili grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>) by invasive African grasses in the Hawaiian Islands. <i>Pacific Science</i> 52 (3): 220–227.</p> <p>Goergen E, Daehler CC. (2002) Factors affecting seedling recruitment in an invasive grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) and a native grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>) in the Hawaiian Islands. <i>Plant Ecology</i>, 161 (2): 147–156.</p> <p>Joubert DF, Cunningham PL. (2002) The distribution and invasive potential of fountain grass <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> in Namibia. <i>Dinteria</i>, 27: 37–47.</p>	
IMP1b: Predation	
Response: NA	Confidence:
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a plant.	
References:	
IMP1c: Hybridisation	
Response: Minimal Concern (MC)	Confidence: Medium
<p>Rationale: A laboratory study by Dujardin and Hanna (1989) demonstrated the ability for pearl millet (<i>Cenchrus americanus</i>) and fountain grass (<i>C. setaceus</i>) to hybridise. “Twenty and 28 interspecific hybrids, respectively, were produced between diploid ($2n = 14$) pearl millet and <i>P. orientate</i> L. C. Rich. ($2n = 36$), and <i>C. setaceus</i> (Forssk.) Chiov. ($2n = 27$).” (Dujardin and Hanna 1989). <i>Cenchrus americanus</i> occurs in KNP where it was first recorded in the gardens of Pretoriuskop. There is no evidence of hybridisation between <i>C. setaceus</i> and <i>C. americanus</i> in natural ecosystems. Therefore, impact of <i>C. setaceus</i> through hybridisation with native species is of minimal concern.</p>	
References:	
<p>Dujardin M, Hanna WW. (1989) Crossability of pearl millet with wild <i>Pennisetum</i> species. <i>Crop science</i> 29 (1): 77–80.</p>	
IMP1d: Transmission of disease	
Response: Data Deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale: No data found	
References:	
IMP1e: Parasitism	
Response: NA	Confidence:
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is not parasitic.	
References:	
IMP1f: Poisoning/toxicity	

Response: Data Deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale: No data found.	
References:	
IMP1g: Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	
Response: Data Deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale: No data found.	
References:	
IMP1h: Grazing/herbivory/browsing	
Response: NA	Confidence:
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a plant.	
References:	
IMP1i: Chemical, physical or structural impact on ecosystem	
Response: Moderate (MO)	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> has a pronounced negative impact on below-ground resource acquisition use by the dominant native trees of the north Kona dry forest ecosystem of Hawaii (Cordell and Sandquist 2008). Carbon allocation patterns and water use functions of native <i>Diospyros</i> spp. which are the most dominant tree species of the north Kona dry forest ecosystem were significantly changed by <i>C. setaceus</i> invasion. Cordell and Sandquist (2008) concluded that the coexistence of native dry forest trees and the alien <i>fountain grass</i> was not sustainable in this ecosystem and that in spite of management efforts the death of most dry forest trees will occur as a result of <i>Cenchrus</i>' invasion in the understory.</p> <p>The monotypic stands of <i>C. setaceus</i> dead mass increase fire intensity and frequency which cause a physical impact on ecosystems (Adkins et al. 2011, Tunison 1992). A study by Rahlao et al. (2009) indicates that <i>C. setaceus</i> invasion may increase fire frequency and intensity in the arid ecosystems of South Africa. In Hawaii where it invades lava flows, disrupting primary succession by preventing colonization of native species (Adkins et al. 2011, Tunison 1992). A study by Rodríguez-Cabellero et al. (2017) indicates that <i>C. setaceus</i> interacts with the soil bacteria community, shifting the community's structure, composition, and nitrogen cycling.</p> <p>Thus far, impact cause by <i>C. setaceus</i> on native ecosystems is moderate because there is no evidence of local extinction of a native species due to <i>C. setaceus</i> invasion.</p>	
References:	
Adkins E, Cordell S, Drake DR. (2011) Role of fire in the germination ecology of fountain grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>), an invasive African bunchgrass in Hawai'i. <i>Pacific Science</i> , 65 (1): 17–25.	
Cordell S, Sandquist DR. (2008) The impact of an invasive African bunchgrass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) on water availability and productivity of canopy trees within a tropical dry forest in Hawaii. <i>Functional Ecology</i> , 22 (6): 1008–1017.	
Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Van Wilgen BW, Barnard P. (2009) Effects of invasion of fire-free arid shrublands by a fire-promoting invasive alien grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) in South Africa. <i>Austral Ecology</i> , 34 (8): 920–928.	
Rodríguez-Caballero G, Caravaca F, Alguacil MM, Fernández-López M, Fernández-González AJ, Roldán A. (2017) Striking alterations in the soil bacterial community structure and functioning of the biological N cycle induced by <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> invasion in a semiarid environment. <i>Soil Biology and Biochemistry</i> , 109: 176–187.	
Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i: management and research. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376–393.	
IMP1k: Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	
Response: Minor (MN)	Confidence: Medium
Rationale:	
<i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> and <i>C. ciliaris</i> grasslands inhibit shrub colonization through competition with shrub seedlings for water (Daehler and Carino 1998). Impact cause by <i>C. setaceus</i> on native species	

through interaction with other alien species is of minor concern because evidence of population decline as a result of the interaction was not found.	
References: Daehler CC, Carino DA. (1998) Recent replacement of native pili grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>) by invasive African grasses in the Hawaiian Islands. <i>Pacific Science</i> 52 (3): 220–227.	
IMP1 Maximum environmental impact (Figure S2)	
Response: Major (MR)	Confidence: High
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> has been reported to cause major impacts through competition with native species which has led to local extinction of some native grass species in island ecosystems (Cordell and Sandquist 2008, Daehler and Carino 1998, Goergen and Daehler 2002).	
References: Cordell S, Sandquist DR. (2008) The impact of an invasive African bunchgrass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) on water availability and productivity of canopy trees within a tropical dry forest in Hawaii. <i>Functional Ecology</i> , 22 (6): 1008–1017. Daehler CC, Carino DA. (1998) Recent replacement of native pili grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>) by invasive African grasses in the Hawaiian Islands. <i>Pacific Science</i> 52 (3): 220–227. Goergen E, Daehler CC. (2002) Factors affecting seedling recruitment in an invasive grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) and a native grass (<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>) in the Hawaiian Islands. <i>Plant Ecology</i> , 161 (2): 147–156.	

IMP2 Socio-economic impact	
IMP2a: Safety	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
IMP2b: Material and immaterial assets	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
IMP2c: Health	
Response: Minimal Concern (MC)	Confidence: Medium
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> produces high amounts of pollen (Pollen Library 2022). The pollen of <i>C. setaceus</i> is extremely light, float off easily in the wind and thus cause many problems for people with allergies (ASI 2022, Botanical-online 2022). Evidence of <i>C. setaceus</i> causing severe allergic or asthmatic impact was not found, therefore the impact is of minimal concern.	
References: Asthma Society of Ireland (ASI). (2022) Allergies & creating an allergy free garden. Dublin, Ireland. https://www.asthma.ie/sites/default/files/files/document_bank/2018/May/ASI%20-%20Gardening%20with%20Asthma%20-%2000518%20-%2003.pdf Botanical-online. (2022) Plants that produce allergies. https://www.botanical-online.com/en/botany/allergic-plants Pollen Library. (2022) Fountain Grass (<i>Pennisetum</i>) Genus Level Details & Allergy Info. https://www.pollenlibrary.com/Genus/Pennisetum/	
IMP2d: Social, spiritual and cultural relations	
Response: Data deficient (DD)	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	
IMP2 Maximum socio-economic impact (Figure S2)	
Response: Minimal Concern	Confidence: Medium
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> pollen causes respiratory health problems for people with allergy.	
References:	

Asthma Society of Ireland (ASI). (2022) Allergies & creating an allergy free garden. Dublin, Ireland. https://www.asthma.ie/sites/default/files/files/document_bank/2018/May/ASI%20-%20Gardening%20with%20Asthma%20-%200518%20-%2003.pdf

Botanical-online. (2022) Plants that produce allergies. <https://www.botanical-online.com/en/botany/allergic-plants>

Pollen Library. (2022) Fountain Grass (*Pennisetum*) Genus Level Details & Allergy Info. <https://www.pollenlibrary.com/Genus/Pennisetum/>

IMP3 Closely related species' environmental impact	
Response: NA	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

IMP4 Closely related species' socio-economic impact	
Response: NA	Confidence:
Rationale:	
References:	

IMP5 Potential impact (based on traits, experiments, or models)	
Response: Moderate (MO)	Confidence: Low
<p>Rationale:</p> <p>Potential impact on native animals: <i>C. setaceus</i> is unpalatable and not a preferred grazing grass due to its low nutritional value (Henderson 2001, Milton et al. 1998). The invasion of <i>C. setaceus</i> in the KNP has the potential to reduce grazing capacity through competition with native grasses, and ultimately reducing nutrition for grazers.</p> <p>Potential impact on safety: Although <i>C. setaceus</i> mostly invades disturbed roadsides, railways, and waterways (ISSA 2021, Milton et al. 1998, Rahlao et al. 2010), wildfires promoted by <i>C. setaceus</i> causes socio-economic impacts that affect activities related to the human safety. For example, personal safety of people and fire-fighting personnel during evacuations.</p> <p>Potential impact on social relations: Nature-based tourism is also affected in areas such as the Western Cape province where invasive grasses including <i>C. setaceus</i> displace indigenous species and affect native floral diversity (homemakers, 2021). Although no deleterious impact has been reported, this impact on conservation tourism can impact human social life.</p> <p>The information sources are of low quality and only inferred data has been used to support the assessment the level of confidence is therefore low.</p>	
<p>References:</p> <p>Henderson L. (2001) Alien Weeds and Invasive Plants: a Complete Guide to Declared Weeds and Invaders in South Africa. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook, 12.</p> <p>Homemakers. (2021) Close Encounters of the Botanical Kind. https://www.homemakersonline.co.za/close-encounters-with-invasive-species/. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p> <p>Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>. http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p> <p>Milton SJ, Hoffmann JH, Bowie RCK, D'amico J, Griffiths M, Joubert D, Loewenthal D, Moinde NN, Seymour C, Toral-Granda MV, Wiseman R. (1998) Invasive fountain grass on the Cape Peninsula. South African Journal of Science 94 (2): 57–58.</p> <p>Milton SJ, Hoffmann JH, Bowie RCK, D'amico J, Griffiths M, Joubert D, Loewenthal D, Moinde NN, Seymour C, Toral-Granda MV, Wiseman R. (1998) Invasive fountain grass on the Cape Peninsula. South African Journal of Science 94 (2): 57–58.</p> <p>Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.</p>	

CALCULATIONS FOR THE IMPACT SCORE: = Major (MR)

Parameter	Mechanism/sector	Response
IMP1a	Competition	MR
IMP1b	Predation	DD
IMP1c	Hybridisation	MC
IMP1d	Disease transmission	DD
IMP1e	Parasitism	NA
IMP1f	Poisoning/toxicity	DD
IMP1g	Bio-fouling or other direct physical disturbance	DD
IMP1h	Grazing/herbivory/browsing	NA
IMP1i	Chemical, physical, structural impact	MO
IMP1k	Indirect impacts through interactions with other species	MN
IMP1	Maximum environmental impact	MR
IMP2a	Safety	DD
IMP2b	Material and immaterial assets	DD
IMP2c	Health	MC
IMP2d	Social, spiritual and cultural relations	DD
IMP2	Maximum socio-economic impact	MC
IMP3	Environmental impact of closely related taxa (only score if IMP1a-k are all DD, otherwise NA)	NA
IMP4	Socio-economic impact of closely related taxa (only score if IMP2a-g are all DD, otherwise NA)	NA
IMP5	Potential impact based on traits, experiments, or models	MO

SUMMARY: RISK SCORE = High

		Impacts				
		MC	MN	MO	MR	MV
Likelihood	Extremely unlikely	low	low	low	medium	medium
	Very unlikely	low	low	low	medium	high
	Unlikely	low	low	medium	high	high
	Fairly probable	medium	medium	high	high	high
	Probable	medium	high	high	high	high

4. Management

MAN1 What is the feasibility to stop future immigration?	
Response: Low	Confidence: Medium
<p>Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> was initially introduced into the KNP for ornamental purposes (Foxcroft et al. 2003). Regulations that prohibit the intentional introduction of live plants or propagules have now been adopted by the parks and nurseries within the park have been mandated to only trade indigenous plant species. Seeds of <i>C. setaceus</i> can be ordered online and delivered by mail. Outside the park <i>C. setaceus</i> is dominant in places frequented by humans, along the roads (Rahlao et al. 2010), which decreases the feasibility of stopping future immigrations. Even so, since this pathway is human aided, it is much easier to regulate than unintentional pathways as <i>C. setaceus</i> can also be dispersed by wind, waterways, and birds (Fish et al. 2015, Henderson 2001, Rahlao et al. 2010). The feasibility to stop future immigration is therefore low because of the multiple potential re-introduction pathways.</p>	
<p>References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. Koedoe, 46 (2): 21–44. Henderson L. (2001) Alien Weeds and Invasive Plants: a Complete Guide to Declared Weeds and Invaders in South Africa. Plant Protection Research Institute Handbook, 12. Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.</p>	
MAN2 Benefits of the Species	
MAN2a Socio-economic benefits of the Species	
Response: Low	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale: The socio-economic importance of <i>C. setaceus</i> lies in its use as a garden ornamental (Fish et al. 2015). Due to its invasiveness <i>C. setaceus</i> is nowadays less widely sold in nurseries, and cultivars such as the purple fountain grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> 'rubrum' or <i>P. advena</i> Wipff & Veldkamp) have been developed and are promoted for their sterility (Fish et al. 2015). Although <i>C. setaceus</i> has some economic value for the horticultural industry in South Africa, its trade within the KNP is not permitted. This is because the mandate of protected areas such as the KNP is to protect and conserve the natural biodiversity. Native grasses such as <i>Melinis nerviglumis</i>, <i>Melinis repens</i>, <i>Themeda triandra</i>, <i>Chlorophytum saundersiae</i> can be used to serve as ornamentals within the park instead of the invasive <i>C. setaceus</i> (ISSA 2021).</p> <p>The socio-economic benefits of <i>C. setaceus</i> within the context of KNP are assessed as low because alien species are not permitted in KNP.</p>	
<p>References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>. http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum. Accessed 20-04-2021.</p>	
MAN2b Environmental benefits of the Species	
Response: Low	Confidence: High
<p>Rationale:</p>	

According to ISSA (2021) *C. setaceus* has been used for soil stabilisation particularly on mine spoil in South Africa, however, this is not the primary reason for the *Species*' introduction in the country. Additionally, land uses or commercial prospecting (mining) that negatively impact the native ecosystems of the KNP are not allowed/part of the designated land use of a national park and are restricted according to the National Environmental Management: Protected Areas Act (NEMPAA) of 2003. The usage of *C. setaceus* for soil stabilization within the KNP is low (prohibited) as native grass species such as *Cynodon dactylon* can be used instead of *C. setaceus*, and no new alien species may be introduced into the park.

Birds utilise dry *C. setaceus* for nest construction but not exclusively (Mygardenlife 2021), other dry grasses can be used in the absence if fountain grass.

References:
 Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - *Pennisetum setaceum*. <http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum>. Accessed 20-04-2021.
 Mygardenlife. (2021) Fountain Grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*). <https://www.mygardenlife.com/plant-library/2206/pennisetum/setaceum>. Accessed 29-06-2021.

MAN3 Ease of management

MAN3a How accessible are populations?

Response: 1 (Moderately accessible)	Confidence: Medium
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Rationale:
 Outside the Area, and in South African generally, *C. setaceus* grows in disturbed areas such as roadsides and waste dumps that are easily accessible (Fish et al. 2015). Rahlao et al. (2010) indicate that *C. setaceus* grows in road-river interchanges that are inaccessible during roadside management. In other areas where it has been introduced - such as the island of Hawai'i – *C. setaceus* occurs in high elevation ranges of about 2600m a.s.l. (GISD 2021, Williams and Black 1993) and on steep rocky outcrops which can be difficult or dangerous to access.
 In the KNP *C. setaceus* was recorded as a riparian invader outside containment (gardens), however, this has not been confirmed (Foxcroft et al. 2003). It is also not known whether *C. setaceus* occurs in high elevations within the Area as in other introduced ranges.
 Plant populations growing in human disturbed habits can be easily accessed, but those found along riverine habitats may be less accessible due to dangerous animals and dense vegetation (i.e. reedbeds and dense thickets). Accessibility within KNP is therefore rated as moderate because some populations can be easily reached while others occur in difficult to reach habitats.

References:
 Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria.
 Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. Koedoe, 46 (2): 21–44.
 Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). (2021) Species profile: *Cenchrus setaceus*. <http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=309>. Accessed on 23-04-2021.
 Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive *Pennisetum setaceum* along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.
 Williams DG, Black RA. (1993) Phenotypic variation in contrasting temperature environments: growth and photosynthesis in *Pennisetum setaceum* from different altitudes on Hawaii. Functional Ecology, 623–633.

MAN3b Is the *Species* hard to detect?

Response: 1 (easily detectible for most of the year.)	Confidence: Medium
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Rationale:
 Fountain grass is easily identified by its feathery, spike-like inflorescence which are reddish or pinkish in colour (ISSA 2021). Detectability can be difficult during periods where *C. setaceus* does not have

the bright effloresces (Rahlao et al. 2010). However, <i>C. setaceus</i> stay in flower for most part of the year, from November to July in Southern African (Fish et al. 2015).	
References: Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria. Invasive Species South Africa (ISSA). (2021) Fountain grass - <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> . http://www.invasives.org.za/component/k2/item/299-fountain-grass-pennisetum-setaceum . Accessed 20-04-2021. Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2010) The distribution of invasive <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> along roadsides in western South Africa: the role of corridor interchanges. Weed research, 50(6): 537–543.	
MAN3c Time to reproduction	
Response: 2 (less than one year)	Confidence: High
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> can reproduce apomictically or by seeds (Bossard et al. 2000, Williams et al. 1995), and reproduction starts within one year of germination. <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> has the ability to form pseudo-vivipary plantlets when inflorescences are inundated (Milton et al. 2008). Plantlet production through pseudo-vivipary may facilitate the rapid spread of <i>C. setaceus</i> , especially in seasonally flooding rivers in arid regions (Milton et al 2008).	
References: Bossard CC, Randall JM, Hoshovsky MC. (2000) Invasive Plants of California's Wildlands. University of California Press, Berkeley. Milton SJ, Dean WRJ, Rahlao SJ. (2008) Evidence for induced pseudo-vivipary in <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> (fountain grass) invading a dry river, arid Karoo, South Africa. South African Journal of Botany, 74 (2): 348–349. Williams DG, Mack RN, Black RA. (1995) Ecophysiology of introduced <i>Pennisetum setaceum</i> on Hawaii: the role of phenotypic plasticity. Ecology, 76 (5): 1569–1580.	
MAN3d Propagule persistence	
Response: 3 (more than five years)	Confidence: High
Rationale: Individual plants may live up to 20 years, and seeds may remain viable in the soil for six to seven years (Bossard et al. 2000, Donaldson and Rafferty 2002, Tunison 1992).	
References: Bossard CC, Randall JM, Hoshovsky MC. (2000) Invasive Plants of California's Wildlands. University of California Press, Berkeley. Donaldson S, Rafferty D. (2002) Identification and Management of fountain grass (<i>Pennisetum Setaceum</i> Forsk. Chiov.). University of Nevada-Reno, Cooperative extension. Fact Sheet-02–50 Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i: management and research. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376–393.	
MAN3 Ease of management (SUM calculated from the Table below)	
Response: Difficult (>5)	Confidence: High
Rationale: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is moderately accessible in South Africa and it is in flower for at least nine months of the year, making it easy to identify during that period. <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> can start reproducing within one year of germination, whole plants are long-lived up to 20 years and the seeds stay viable for more than six years. See also responses above.	
References: See above	
MAN4 Has the feasibility of extirpation or eradication been evaluated?	

Response: No	Confidence: Low
<p>Rationale: The feasibility of eradicating <i>C. setaceus</i> has not been evaluated in the Kruger National Park or in South Africa thus far (Rahlao et al. 2014). Eradication programs have been developed and trailed in other introduced ranges. For example, <i>C. setaceus</i> has been part of the Volcanoes resource management in Hawai'i since the early 1960s (Tunison 1992). It is unknown whether an eradication feasibility evaluation was conducted before the start of the programme, but according to Tunison (1992), data on the treatment effectiveness, distribution, and workload requirements have been collected since the 1979. Despite eradication efforts, <i>C. setaceus</i> is still invasive in Hawaii. Factors such as, control options, costs, and the overall distribution of <i>C. setaceus</i> within the KNP need to be determined in order to evaluate eradication feasibility.</p>	
<p>References: Rahlao SJ, Milton SJ, Esler KJ, Barnard P. (2014) Performance of invasive alien fountain grass (<i>Pennisetum setaceum</i>) along a climatic gradient through three South African biomes. South African Journal of Botany, 91: 43–48. Tunison JT. (1992) Fountain Grass Control in Hawai'i Volcanoes National Park: management considerations and strategies. Alien plant invasions in native ecosystems of Hawai'i: management and research. Cooperative National Parks Resources Studies Unit, University of Hawai'i at Manoa Honolulu, 376-393.</p>	

MAN5 What is the range size of the <i>Species</i> in the Area.	
Response: Small (< 10 %)	Confidence: Medium
<p>Rationale: The invasion status of <i>C. setaceus</i> was reported by Foxcroft et al. (2003, 2008) as “naturalised” in riparian/riverine areas and the staff villages of the KNP. However, populations of <i>C. setaceus</i> are rarely found since the formation of the alien biota team, whose mandate is to remove ornamental alien species within the developed areas of the KNP and to act as a rapid response team against new emerging infestations. Although surveys for <i>C. setaceus</i> infestations have not been conducted across all riverine systems of the KNP, experts are confident to say that the range size of <i>C. setaceus</i> within the park is not more than 10 % or less.</p>	
<p>References: Foxcroft LC, Henderson L, Nichols GR, Martin BW. (2003) A revised list of alien plants for the Kruger National Park. Koedoe, 46 (2): 21–44. Foxcroft LC, Richardson DM, Wilson JR (2008) Ornamental Plants as Invasive Aliens: Problems and Solutions in Kruger National Park, South Africa. Environmental Management, 41: 32–51.</p>	

MAN6 What are the control options and management actions available for the <i>Species</i>?	
Response: Monitoring and Prevention	Confidence: Medium
<p>Rationale: Control options: No herbicide has been registered for use on <i>C. setaceus</i> in any part of South Africa including the KNP. According to Szatab and Henderson (2016), foliar herbicides appear to be ineffective but isolated plants may be controlled mechanically by uprooting them or destroying them with a weed eater (GISD 2021). Biological control has not been explored for the control of <i>C. setaceus</i> either. Integrated control using both chemical and mechanical control may be effective for large infestations. Management actions: Population of <i>C. setaceus</i> that previously occurred in the staff villages of KNP have been control and removed by the Alien Biota clearing team and there are no known naturalised populations of <i>C. setaceus</i> outside residential areas of the park (LC. Foxcroft, pers. comm. 2021). However, monitoring for <i>C. setaceus</i> should be conducted along the boundaries and riverine habits of the parks (LC. Foxcroft, pers. comm. 2021). Measures to prevent the introduction of <i>C. setaceus</i> from outside the park around the Phalaborwa area should be taken (LC. Foxcroft, pers. comm. 2021).</p>	
<p>References: Global Invasive Species Database (GISD). (2021) Species profile: <i>Cenchrus setaceus</i>. http://www.iucngisd.org/gisd/species.php?sc=309. Accessed on 23-04-2021.</p>	

Sztab L, Henderson L. (2016) ARC-PPRI fact sheets on invasive alien plants and their control in South Africa: fountain grass (*Pennisetum setaceum*). Infoweeds@arc.agric.za

MAN7 Any other management considerations that need to be highlighted?

Response:

It should be highlighted that a sterile cultivar of *C. setaceus* named *Pennisetum setaceum* 'rubrun' has been created and is sold in nurseries around South Africa. The cultivar is promoted for its sterility and non-invasiveness, however there is no scientific evidence to support the sterility claims. Hybrids and sterile cultivars of *C. setaceus* are not listed in the NEMBA regulations of 2016.

The sterile cultivar (*Pennisetum setaceum* 'rubrum') has been recorded by Keet et al. (submitted) within the KNP, in Skukuza camp. The spread of the cultivars may complicate management efforts within the KNP, they should therefore be equally prioritised, and such prohibited for importation under the KNP ornamental plant policy.

References:

Fish L, Mashau AC, Moeaha MJ, Nembudani MT. (2015) Identification guide to southern African grasses. An identification manual with keys, descriptions and distributions. Strelitzia 36. South African National Biodiversity Institute, Pretoria.

Keet J-H, Foxcroft LC, Kumschick S, Nichols GR, Richardson DM, Wilson JRU, Datta A. (submitted) Assessing the effectiveness of alien plant regulations: insights from Kruger National Park, South Africa.

CALCULATION FOR THE EASE OF MANAGEMENT SCORE = Difficult

Parameter	Question	Response/Score
MAN3a	How accessible are populations?	1
MAN3b	Is the <i>Species</i> hard to detect?	1
MAN3c	Time to reproduction	2
MAN3d	Propagule persistence	3
MAN3	SUM	7

5. Communication

<p>Recommended goal:</p> <p>The recommended goal will be one of the following: <i>Potential eradication target:</i> Requires urgent assessment of cost / budgeting; implement rapid response control; distribution survey-finding all individuals; implement sustained control programme. <i>Potential Containment target:</i> Eradication unlikely, but same as above generally; aim at the population level (contain and reduce the abundance of the population). <i>Long-term Control programme:</i> Schedule into future clearing project cycles/contracts <i>Monitoring/surveillance:</i> Not a priority for management, however surveillance / distribution should be initiated and trends assessed.</p>	<p>Priority level:</p> <p>The recommended goal will be one of the following: <i>High priority:</i> Should receive immediate management attention. <i>Medium priority:</i> Schedule for control if ease of control is high. <i>Low priority:</i> Do not prioritise for eradication or management/control, except follow-up assessments to ensure ornamental plants previously removed do not regrow.</p>
<p>Motivation:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is listed in the NEMBA regulation under category 1b excluding sterile cultivars and hybrids. It was introduced into the KNP as an ornamental in four sites. It has since been removed from the gardens in the staff village. The overall extent or current distribution of <i>C. setaceus</i> outside cultivation is unknown.</p> <p>Management feasibility plan for <i>C. setaceus</i> has not been conducted for the park or similar habitats and <i>C. setaceus</i> should not be prioritised for a feasibility study as it is low-priority <i>Species</i> as per the framework. Invasive populations outside cultivation and other disturbed areas (e.g. roadsides) have not been recorded, however <i>C. setaceus</i> is a riparian species therefore surveillance in riverine habitats should be considered. Surveillance around the Phalaborwa mines and KNP boundaries should be conducted as <i>C. setaceus</i> is used for sand stabilisation in the mines. Mechanical methods of eradication (whole plant removal) should be used for individuals found in the park and herbicide trials should be conducted. For large infestation a combination of chemical and mechanical control methods is recommended</p>	<p>Motivation:</p> <p><i>Cenchrus setaceus</i> is a high-risk species as it has been reported to cause major environmental impacts through competition with native plant species. It can alter the structure and physical properties of native ecosystems by changing fire regimes. Management of <i>C. setaceus</i> is also difficult due to the long-lived seeds (>5 years), and short time to reproduction (less than 1 year).</p> <p>The recommendation is for <i>C. setaceus</i> to be categorised as a low priority species in the KNP, with follow-up control on ornamental plants previously removed and long-term surveillance along high-risk area.</p>

Appendices

Appendix BAC7: A map of the native range.

Figure 1: Map of the native range of *Cenchrus setaceus* native in Northern and Eastern Africa, Middle East and South-west Asia. <https://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/116202#toDistributionMaps>. Accessed 20-04-2021.

Appendix BAC8: A map of the global alien range.

Figure 2: Global alien distribution of *Cenchrus setaceus*.
https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?country=US&has_coordinate=true&has_geospatial_issue=false&taxon_key=5828232 (accessed 24-08-2020).

Appendix BAC10a: A map of the alien range in the Area.

Figure 3: Distribution of *Cenchrus setaceus* in Kruger National Park. Distribution data from Keet et al. (submitted) and GBIF (2021).

https://www.gbif.org/occurrence/search?country=US&has_coordinate=true&has_geospatial_issue=false&taxon_key=5828232 (accessed 24-08-2020). Keet J-H, Foxcroft LC, Kumschick S, Nichols GR, Richardson DM, Wilson JRU, Datta A. (submitted) Assessing the effectiveness of alien plant regulations: insights from Kruger National Park, South Africa.

Appendix BAC10b: Images of the *Species'* population or individuals in the Area

Figure 4: Populations of *C. setaceus* in the Phalaborwa mining area, outside the borders of KNP, GPS Coordinates: -23.986754, 31.120221

Appendix MAN7: Other Management considerations that need to be highlighted

As stated under MAN7 cultivars of *C. setaceus* are sold in nurseries across South Africa and are marked for their “Sterility”. However, there is no evidence to support the sterility of the cultivars. The sterile cultivar (*Pennisetum setaceum* 'rubrum') has been recorded by Keet et al. (submitted) within the KNP, in Skukuza camp. The spread of the cultivars may complicate management efforts within the KNP.

Cenchrus setaceus is listed under category 1b under the name *Pennisetum setaceus* in the NEMBA Regulations of 2020, this listing excludes all sterile cultivars or hybrids of the species. Although the legislation excludes hybrids and sterile cultivars of *C. setaceus*, experts recommend that the management should equally prioritised all entities of the species within KNP regardless of their sterility.